

Automatic rule verifications for Digital Building Permits

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Abstract

The construction sector is facing major changes in the client and market requirements, pushing towards the digital transformation and a data driven industry. Governments have taken an active part in this change by supporting the digitalization of processes such as the one for building permits by introducing the use of building information models (BIM). The research on the digitalization of the building permit has shown great advancements in regarding the rule extraction in interpretable ways and the automation of the verification; however, the conciliation between the building model semantic definitions and the concepts defined in the regulations is still in discussion. Moreover, the validation of the correctness of the information included in building models regarding the regulation definitions is important to guarantee the quality along the digital building permit process.

This dissertation aims to propose a hybrid workflow to check the information extracted explicitly from the BIM model and the information implicitly derived from relationships between elements by following the provisions contained in the regulations in the context of Portugal. Based on some context and literature review, a process reengineering was proposed, and a Python code was developed using the IfcOpenShell library to support the automation of the verification process, traditionally carried out by technicians in the building permit offices. The elements developed in this document were proven in a case-study, demonstrating that the hybrid validation can help to detect modelling errors and improve the certainty of correctness of information during the initial submission of models for a building permit process.

The results indicate that the inclusion of an automated validation of the model against regulation definitions can be introduced to improve the degree of certainty of the quality of the information contained in the Building Information Model, moreover the proposal of methods that produce results from implicit information can extend the capabilities of the IFC schema. However, the scripts developed in this work are still under constant review and development and have limitations of applicability in relation to certain IFC classes.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/PAqQ1kUrE8w>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7263262